

LIFE STRATEGY IS FAMILY SUCCESS

¹Yavkacheva Z.A., ²Raxmatov F.N.

^{1,2}Tashkent State Transport University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11401785>

Abstract. *What is "Life Strategy" in this article? How to write it, the pros and cons of the strategy are covered in detail. But neither he nor others know how long a person will live. The average life expectancy is 70-80 years. The first twenty-five years of life are spent on gaining knowledge and experience, self-realization. After sixty years, physical abilities decrease, and a person no longer has the same strength as in middle age. For a person, the age range from thirty to sixty years is the most optimal for important achievements and successes.*

If everyone understands that the period of their success is limited, that is, life has a beginning and an end, and there is also a period for doing important things. In this space, a person decides what he will achieve in life, why he came to the world, and how he will benefit society. Therefore, every person should create his life plan, i.e. "Life strategy". , you can fill it with ideas that can inspire you and make your life meaningful. If a person can't create his life strategy, he starts copying others into his life, doing things that only think about himself and are useful to him. Will you live long enough to do the planned work? no? It doesn't matter, but you will realize that you have not wasted your life.

It is not easy for a person to write this strategy, if you force your mind to work in this direction, the strategy will show you long-term success.

Keywords: *nation, pride, strategy, life, determination, courage, discipline, purpose, community.*

INTRODUCTION

Due to the health of the spiritual environment in our republic, all kinds of reforms are being carried out, first of all, adapting to the mind and worldview, the spiritual world, the possibilities of creativity and creativity of citizens are expanding, and the concepts of Motherland, nation, and pride are deepening in them.

A person is always given time to realize his dreams and plans, because our dreams are made of energy, they materialize and come true. Some of our dreams come true in a month, some after ten years. Every thought and imagination has its time to materialize. If we focus our attention on the environment, the sequence of winter, spring, summer and autumn seasons will not be broken, they will not change their place, and all this will be repeated in nature. In the same way, our life is subject to the law of nature's repetition.

METHODS AND RESULTS

This can be explained with a simple life example. Imagine that you are sitting in a restaurant, you order food, and they only bring you the food you ordered, you cannot have what you forgot. Therefore, you are ordering the universe's future through the thoughts written in the "Life Strategy". Fill your life with thoughts that enrich it, not only with material things but also in the form of achievements and successes that fill the meaning of life. Try not to forget anything, for this, a person must be persistent and diligent. Must achieve the best results in life, it is necessary to be independent and get used to self-motivation. Whether your emotions are positive or negative depends on how you talk to yourself every moment. Success in life depends on the skills you

develop over time. Being able to set important goals, not delaying them, and the most important tasks getting used to it is both a mental and a physical skill. This skill can be developed. Starting with the important thing and not leaving it unfinished is a factor that gives quick results. Regardless of the importance big or small, when you complete a task, you have energy - enthusiasm, enthusiasm and self-esteem. a feeling of respect arises. The more important the completed task is, the happier and more resilient you feel, and the more self-confidence you have. Doing important work starts to produce endorphins in the brain. The endorphin release process after completing any task makes a person more positive and active and makes a confident person.

Seven stages guide a person's life to achieve the goal they have set.

Step 1: Figure out what you want.

Step two: Write down your thoughts.

Step three: Set a deadline for your goal, if necessary, divide it into parts and set a separate deadline for each.

Step Four: Make a list of things you need to do to achieve your goal.

Step Five: Turn the list into a plan

Step Six: Begin immediately to execute your plan.

Written goals have a powerful effect on your thinking. They inspire you and motivate you to get to work. It awakens your creativity and unleashes your energy. Goals are the fuel for success. The more ambitious and clear they are, the more you enjoy achieving them. The more you think about your goals, the stronger your desire and inner drive to achieve them will be.

A person living in this society should complete his "Life Strategy" based on the following qualities:

- determination - courage, this is the will of a person to act with confidence without stopping halfway towards his goals;

A determined person tries to allocate his lifetime correctly to achieve his goals. A person may have human qualities, but without courage and determination, his qualities will not benefit anyone. Because a person is smart, polite, educated, hardworking, healthy, and caring, if he is a person if he is a coward, he will not find his place in society.

- courage in thinking - a quality necessary for not being afraid to think differently to one's partners, to prove the superiority of one's ideas, not to be afraid to put them into practice;

- internal discipline - the ability to selflessly mobilize all one's abilities in the way of one's professional development;

- if an idea appears, try to analyze how and why it appeared, to understand;

The need to study worldly sciences and engage in crafts is emphasized even in "Qabusnoma", a didactic work expressed in XI, which expresses the experience and rules of feudal education and upbringing of its time. , geometry, astronomy, music, poetry, and the virtues and benefits of the sciences and arts of rhetoric are shown in separate chapters. Studying the system of sciences in the Renaissance, firstly, studying the perception of the possibility of scientific knowledge in that period, secondly, identifying the trends of advanced views on science, and thirdly, important to considering the achievements of secular sciences as a whole.

- always striving to enrich one's activity with some new, improved elements, in which the influence of the family, the experience of colleagues, science, and economic knowledge sources are always used, collecting them, never being satisfied with the level achieved, and not stopping oneself from completing new problems and tasks.

In his works, Farobi also paid attention to the issues of state management, but he illuminated these issues from the point of view of the realization of the main goal - to make the people happy and happy, and he subordinated them to this goal. Thoughts about the forms of government are important in studying Farobi's legal views. Forms of state management can be different. This diversity is determined by the requirements of the main goal - happiness.

State management requires the presence of various noble qualities that constitute the art of leadership. It refers to a complex of various mental, moral and physical qualities. These qualities are health, bravery, bravery, intelligence, enlightenment, peace-loving, just, state management, deep knowledge of the art of dealing with people and the ability to masterfully apply this knowledge in practice. First of all, justice, and wisdom A person who embodies and perfects his qualities can become the head of the state. Moral qualities and virtues, scientific knowledge, and craft, like various arts, are acquired by a person in the course of his personal life, under the influence of the external environment.

The maturation of a person is a complex process, that is, the internal influence of a person and the external factors that affect a person can be controlled by a person and not depend on him at all. The maturation of a person is related to his personal feelings. To become a perfect person, creating a "Life Strategy" and following it will lead to qualitative changes in a person's psyche and body.

A person does not become a perfect person by birth but is revealed by enduring the trials of life over the years. One of the wise men, Aziziddin Nasafi, defines a perfect person and his human qualities as follows: You know, a perfect person is a person who is mature in Sharia and Tariqat and truth, and if if you don't understand this phrase, say it with another phrase: you know that a perfect person is a person who has perfected the following four things: good words, good deeds, good morals and knowledge.

According to the teaching of "Avesta", good understanding, good thought, good intention, kind words, and good deeds are said to mean kindness to the poor, hospitality, actions that bring praise to a person, jealousy, theft, robbery, etc. The concept of a perfect person was introduced by Muhyiddin Ibn al-Arabi, known as Sheikh Kabir. A person should always strive for perfection. A perfect person's contribution to the development of society is also perfect. A perfect person is distinguished among people by the following qualities: intelligence, politeness, hard work, education, health, national pride, patriotism, brave, fierce, international, patient-contented, humanitarian and generous. A person who lacks spirituality, independent thinking, and worldview will never sacrifice his life for the Motherland. The Motherland is the whole nation that perfects its historical action in this field. This is the nation's past, present, and future. It consists in praying for goodness and enlightenment with sincerity, fervour, and effective desire.

CONCLUSION

A person looks up to the heights and aspires to the faraway places. He becomes restless, brooding over the lost luck and the happiness that never comes. That's all his mistakes! Spirituality and economy, first of all, start from the family. Everyone who lives in the family, the so-called holy homeland, must work for the well-being of the family. Moreover, everyone struggles to live, works hard, and tries to satisfy their material and spiritual needs. That is why there is the most basic philosophy of life. This philosophy is "Life Strategy" " is the basis of this. It is a matter of a drop of water. A single drop of water is powerless, but millions of drops can erode rocks and overcome obstacles. A regular flow of water erodes rock. As you continue to work towards your most important goals, you will be able to achieve success by acting like that water. Although it

takes a lot of energy to overcome laziness and start work, it takes much less energy to continue the work. Like a million drops of water, a person who wants to enter the study of science should be young, humble, in good health, polite and well-educated, determined, and scientific. should be treated with respect. The fun part is that the faster you move, the more energy you get. The faster you work, the more you experience, and the more you learn. and the more work you complete, the higher your self-esteem, self-esteem, and personal pride.

REFERENCES

1. A collection of articles." Use of innovative technologies in the continuous education system". - Tashkent, "Fan publishing house" 2009.
2. Sodikova T. The magic of life - Tashkent: "Uzbekistan", 2016.
3. Son of Akmal Miravaz. The golden key of education or signs on the road - Tashkent: "Movarounnahr", 2018.
4. Yavkacheva Z. THE FAMILY IS THE BASIC LINK OF THE COMMUNITY AND IS THE NEWER // Science and Innovation. - 2022. - T. 1. – no. B 8. – S. 1884-1890
5. Yavkacheva Z., Abdugarimova M. BIOPHYSICAL THEORY – OSNOVA TVORCHESKOY SPOSOBNOSTI //Nauka i innovatsii. - 2023. - T. 2. – no. B3. - S. 456-459.